

CRACK PROPAGATION AND MICROSTRUCTURE IN HOT TORSION AND COLD BENDING PARTICULATE ALUMINUM MATRIX COMPOSITES

Xiaoxin Xia and H.J. McQueen

Department of Mechanical Engineering, Concordia University
1455 De Maisonneuve W., Montreal H3G 1M8, Canada

ABSTRACT

Effects of the reinforcement character, volume fraction, annealing temperature on fracture behavior in either 10 and 20 v% Al_2O_3 or 15 v% SiC particle reinforced 6061 Al matrix composites are studied. The fracture investigations are carried out by torsion test in the temperature range from 200-500 °C with strain rate of 1.0 s^{-1} and by a three point bending test at 25 °C. The microstructure of the specimens are studied by optical, scanning and transmission electron microscope after fracture. The torsion results show that the 15 % SiC reinforced 6061 Al has relatively low ductility among the three composites in the range from 200-500 °C. The bending studies reveal that the energy required to completely propagate a crack for Al_2O_3 /6061 Al composites is much higher than that for the 15% SiC reinforced one in which a much more brittle matrix is observed as a result of precipitation of Mg_2Si or Al_2Cu . Bending energy absorption exhibits a maximum value after a 300 °C anneal, indicating dependence on both matrix ductility and strength. The size of the dimples increases with reduction of the reinforcement volume fraction due to enhanced plastic deformation between voids. For both torsion and bending specimens, crack initiation has been found at the reinforcement/matrix interface, but not from the breaking of the particles.

INTRODUCTION

The particle reinforced metal matrix composites exhibit isotropic properties, high strength and modulus, are more easily processed and relatively less costly compared to fibre reinforced composites, and therefore are very attractive for automotive applications. The relationship of processing, microstructure and fracture behavior of the metal matrix composites have been studied during more than ten years [1-7], with regards to the effects of the reinforcement character, size and volume fraction. The fracture mechanisms of the composites are more complicated because the reinforcements cause local stress concentrations and also offer microstructural discontinuities in front of the crack tip. Some references report that the fracture mechanism of the particle reinforced MMCs is ductile fracture, i.e., continual nucleation, growth and coalescence of the voids to connect with the initial crack and to cause crack propagation. For the high volume fraction particle reinforced MMCs (>15 v%), the fracture mechanism involved very little void growth in full size fracture specimens [8]. Debate

continues regarding void nucleation from debonding of reinforcement/matrix interfaces or from the breaking of the reinforcements. In this paper, the effects of the reinforcement character, volume fraction, deformation or annealing temperatures on the fracture mechanism are discussed by torsion and bending tests. Comparisons of force required to initiate voids and energy required to propagate cracks at 25 °C are discussed in Al₂O₃ and SiC particle reinforced composites with various volume fraction and annealing temperatures.

EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

The 10 v% and 20 v% Al₂O₃ or 15 v% SiC particle reinforced 6061 Al metal matrix composites (MMCs) produced by liquid metal mixing technique are provided by Alcan International Limited, Kingston R & D Center and Duralcan, San Diego. The chemical compositions of the MMCs are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Reinforcement type, size and matrix composition of the MMCs

Reinforcements types	Reinforcement size (µm)	Mg	Cu	Fe	Si	Mn
10% Al ₂ O ₃	20	1.0	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.15
20% Al ₂ O ₃	20	1.0	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.15
15% SiC	18	1.0	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.15

Torsion and bending tests were carried out to investigate the fracture behavior of the MMCs. Torsion specimens were cylindrical with a gauge length of 17.46 mm and diameter of 6.04 mm. The specimens were tested to failure by a servo-hydraulic, computer controlled torsion machine [9] at 200, 300, 400 and 500 °C with strain rate of 1.0 s⁻¹.

Three point bending tests were performed at 25 °C on an Instron machine (code 4505). The bending specimens are single crack and one point loading mode. The specimens are derived from the torsion specimen shoulder and annealed at 200, 300 or 500 °C for 30 mins. The dimensions of the specimens are 20 mm x 7.5 mm x 4 mm with a 4.5 mm precrack as shown in Figure 1. The bending specimens are not the standard size which is not a problem since the aim of the bending tests is to compare the force and energy absorption for the three various volume fraction reinforced composites. However, the small width of the specimens reduce the constraint at the crack tip and permit extensive plastic deformation in the matrix.

After mechanical tests, scanning, transmission electron microscopy (SEM, TEM) and optical microscopy are utilized for microstructural analysis. SEM samples are directly taken from the fresh torsion and bending fracture specimen surface after failure. TEM samples are prepared from the fracture specimen parallel to the specimen axis, and mechanically dimpled and ion-milled to 2000 Å thick for investigation. Optical microscopy is made on initial and polished surfaces transverse to the crack.

Figure 1 The bending specimen dimensions and test device.

RESULTS

The distributions of the SiC and Al₂O₃ reinforcements are exhibited by optical microscopy on the polished sections. The average size of the SiC particles is 18 μm which are relatively uniformly distributed in the 6061 Al matrix. Some casting porosities are found in the matrix (Figure 2). The average size of the Al₂O₃ particles is 20 μm. The distribution of the particles is relatively uniform, but is cellular in character in the 10 % Al₂O₃/6061 Al in relation to primary dendrites; little porosity has been found in the Al₂O₃ reinforced MMCs.

Figure 2 The distributions of the SiC and Al₂O₃ reinforcements. (a) 15 % SiC particles, occasionally casting pores observed, (b) 10% Al₂O₃/6061, cellular matrix areas without particles, (c) 20%Al₂O₃/6061, particle concentration very high in some regions, optical microscopy.

The fracture strain (ϵ_f) versus temperature (T) curves of the torsion specimens are shown in Figure 3. It can be seen that the ϵ_f of the 15 % SiC reinforced MMC has a relatively low value in comparison to 10 % and 20 % Al₂O₃ reinforced MMCs in the range of 200-400 °C. ϵ_f slightly increased to above the 20 % Al₂O₃ reinforced one at 500 °C. SEM investigation shows that the crack propagation in the torsion specimen is related to the reinforcement/matrix debonding (Figure 4). Optical microscopy also shows that the crack propagates from debonding of reinforcement/ matrix interfaces near a torsion specimen surface (Figure 5). TEM investigations show the finer subgrains in the 20 % Al₂O₃ MMC in comparison to the 15 % SiC and 10 % Al₂O₃ reinforced MMCs (Figure 6). These represent only one type of substructure in a very inhomogeneously deformed matrix, some non-cellular substructure is also found by TEM investigations [10-12].

The three-point-bending force versus displacement curves show that rising annealing temperature from 200 to 500 °C increases the forces required to initiate voids in the Al₂O₃ MMCs; but for the 15 % SiC/6061 Al, the force increases as annealing temperature rises from 200 to 300 °C, then it shows a decrease on rising to 500 °C. The energies required to propagate the crack show a maximum value after annealing at 300 °C in both Al₂O₃ and SiC reinforced MMCs (Figure 7). The forces required to initiate voids and energies required to completely propagate the cracks for the specimens with various reinforcement volume fraction and annealing temperatures are given in Table 2.

SEM observations show that a large number of fine precipitates on the 15 % SiC/6061 Al fracture surfaces as well as solidification pores (Figure 8). Small precipitates and casting porosities are not found in the Al₂O₃ reinforced MMCs (Figure 9), though the MMCs have the same 6061 Al matrix. SEM investigations of the bending specimens show that voids initiate from debonding of reinforcement/matrix interfaces, little evidence is found of the breaking of the particles (Figure 10). As a result of raising the reinforcement volume fraction from 10 % to 20 %, the dimple size is decreased (Figure 11); however, the sizes of the dimples are still bigger than that of the reinforcements themselves.

Table 2 Force and energy absorption for Al₂O₃ and SiC reinforced MMCs

MMCs	Force (N)			Energy absorption (J x 10 ³)		
	200 _{an.}	300 _{an.}	500 _{an.} °C	200 _{an.}	300 _{an.}	500 _{an.} °C
10% Al ₂ O ₃	390	580	1080	33.5	48.4	44.6
20% Al ₂ O ₃		650	1250		55.9	41.9
15% SiC	400	800	505	9.3	14.9	12.6

Figure 3 ϵ_f -T curves of SiC & Al₂O₃/6061 MMCs, torsioned from 200-500°C, 1.0s⁻¹.

Figure 5 Voids initiate at reinforcement/matrix interfaces and link together; torsioned 300°C, 0.1 s⁻¹.

Figure 4. The torsion fracture surface exhibits debonded particles and cusps (altered by rubbing) thus indicating that crack propagation is related to the reinforcements, 20% Al₂O₃/6061 MMC, tested at 300 °C, 1 s⁻¹, taken by SEM.

DISCUSSION

The torsion results show that the ductilities of the MMCs increase with rising test temperature and decreasing reinforcement volume fraction and strain rate [10]. Increasing temperature raises the subgrain size and decreases the dislocation density due to matrix dynamic recovery [10,11]. Local dynamic recrystallization has been found as the deformation temperature rises above 200°C which also improves the ductility [10-13]. It is notable that the 15 % SiC reinfor-

Figure 6 The subgrain sizes of (a) 15 % SiC /6061 Al, (b) 10 % Al₂O₃/6061 Al, (c) 20 % Al₂O₃/6061 Al MMCs, torsion tested at 300 °C , 5 s⁻¹.

Figure 7 The force versus displacement curves of the SiC and Al₂O₃ reinforced MMCs, annealed at 200, 300 or 500 °C, (a) 15 % SiC/6061 Al, (b) 10 % and 20 % Al₂O₃/6061 Al.

ced MMC has a relatively low ductility among the three MMCs with the same matrix in the range from 200-400 °C which may be due to the more intense precipitation of Mg₂Si or Al₂Cu; the extra precipitates may arise from the unclear processing history. The bending results show that in the 200 °C annealed condition, SiC and Al₂O₃ reinforced MMCs require similar force to initiate voids. As the annealing temperature increases to 300 °C, the forces required to open the voids are increased which is due to additional relief of matrix stress concentration. The force required to open the voids increases in the Al₂O₃/6061 Al in 500 °C annealed condition, but it decreases in the SiC/6061 Al which may be explained by the greater precipitate growth which causes matrix strength decrease in the latter. The forces are greater for the 20 % Al₂O₃/6061 MMC than for the 10 % Al₂O₃/6061 due to its greater strength from the particle reinforcement. The energy absorption for crack propagation shows that 200 °C annealed specimens require the lowest energy level in the three MMCs. A maximum energy absorption in the 300 °C annealed condition is linked to the reduced matrix stress concentration which brings both a higher force level and a more ductile matrix. For the three MMCs, the 500 °C annealed specimens show much less energy absorption than that in the 300 °C annealed specimens (Table 2). The force drops with propagation of cracks due to the presence of precipitates which give rise to

Figure 8. On the bending fracture surface, small precipitates on the large dimples from SiC particles are observed by SEM, 15% SiC/6061 Al, (a) in 200 °C annealed, without dimples of their own, (b) in 500 °C annealed, mainly with dimples of their own.

Figure 9. The equiaxed dimples show a ductile fracture mode during bending tests. in the Al_2O_3 /6061Al MMCs, annealed at 300°C, (a) 10% Al_2O_3 /6061 MMC, (b) 20 % Al_2O_3 /6061 Al MMC with small dimples (note change in magnification).

Figure 10. Comparison of SEM observations of the reinforcement/matrix interfaces, (a)15%SiC/6061,200°C annealed, Mg_2Si or Al_2Cu type of precipitates with solidification porosities in center; (b) 20% Al_2O_3 /6061 Al, 300°C annealed, debonding between Al_2O_3 and matrix, precipitates can be observed in the dimples of annealing.

Figure 11 The size of the dimples has been found to decrease with the increase of the reinforcement volume fraction, (a) 10%Al₂O₃/6061Al MMC, (b) 20%Al₂O₃/6061 Al MMC.

additional small voids and reduced plastic tearing. The bending results show that the fracture behavior of the composites depend not only on the matrix strength and stress concentration, but also on the matrix ductility which is affected by the size and interface condition of the precipitates.

The SEM photographs exhibit much larger dimples in the 10 % Al₂O₃ than that in the 20 % Al₂O₃ MMCs which is the result firstly of greater spacing of the particles and secondly of the much more ductile matrix in the 10 % Al₂O₃ reinforced MMC due to less Δ CTE dislocations and particle constraint. The sizes of the dimples decrease in the order 10 % Al₂O₃, 15 % SiC and 20 % Al₂O₃. In the last, the size of the dimples are still bigger than those of the reinforcements indicating that the matrix between the reinforcements does flow during crack propagation which is different from the previous results [8] in full size specimens where the void size is little different from the reinforcement size when the volume fraction is over 15 v%. The SEM and optical microscopy investigations of the fracture surfaces of the torsion and bending specimens give evidence that the voids nucleate at the reinforcement/matrix interfaces, and not from the breaking of the particles, in good agreement with previous investigations [5]. The fracture mechanism of the MMCs is: (I) debonding at the large reinforcement/matrix interfaces, (II) voids grow and (III) voids connect to the main crack thus causing crack propagation.

CONCLUSIONS

- The ductility of the MMCs increases with rising deformation temperature and with decreasing volume fraction. It is also reduced by the reinforcement type, namely SiC.
- Increasing annealing temperature from 200 to 500 °C reduces the matrix stress concentration and strength which brings a more ductile matrix, therefore the energy absorption level for the crack propagation is generally increased. The slightly decrease of the energy level in the 500 °C annealed condition shows that the precipitates growing and developing interfaces reduce the deformation during crack propagation. Increased volume fraction generally raises the energy absorption level because it brings a stronger matrix. The complex variation of forces and energies for crack propagation indicates void initiation and crack propagation depend on a combination of the composite strength, the matrix ductility and precipitate/matrix interface condition.
- The 15% SiC reinforced MMC requires much less energy to propagate the crack completely in comparison to the Al₂O₃ reinforced MMCs in the same test condition, as a result of: (I) the

Mg₂Si or Al₂Cu precipitates making the matrix less ductile, and (II) the matrix casting porosities.

•Raising the particle volume fraction from 10 to 20% decreases the dimple size because of the reduced matrix volume fraction between reinforcements and the much higher ΔCT_E dislocations and particle geometrical constraint which restricts the plastic flow during deformation.

•The torsion and bending tests show that the cracks initiate at reinforcement/matrix interfaces, but not from the breaking of particles in the MMCs studied.

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